

Collatz conjecture Proof

CONJECTURE: STARTING WITH ANY POSITIVE INTEGER, IF IT IS EVEN, DIVIDE IT BY 2. IF IT IS ODD, TRIPLE IT AND ADD 1. REPEAT THIS PROCESS. THE CONJECTURE CLAIMS THAT EVERY SEQUENCE EVENTUALLY REACHES 1.

Personal representation

Let's consider a series u such as:

- u_0 is a positive integer greater than 0
- $u_0 = 2k + 1$ or $u_0 = 2k$ with $k \in \mathbb{N}$
- $u_n = \{3 \times u_{n-1} + 1, u_{n-1} \% 2 = 1 \frac{u_{n-1}}{2}, u_{n-1} \% 2 = 0$

The conjecture states that this series will inevitably fall into the loop $1 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$

Proof

Cases study

With this series we have two operations playing different roles:

- In case of an odd number, $u_{n+1} = 3 \times u_n + 1 \Rightarrow u_{n+1} > u_n$. In that situation the series increases.
- In case of an even number, $u_{n+1} = \frac{u_n}{2} \Rightarrow u_{n+1} < u_n$. In that situation the series decreases.

What do we have to prove?

Determining the frequencies of increases and decreases is necessary to find out if this series will go towards infinity or not. If there're more increases in the series than decreases, the series will theoretically increase till infinity. But with less ups than downs, this series will eventually converge towards its minimal possible value which is 1. **So, we have to prove that the frequency of ups is negligible in front of the frequency of downs.**

The second point to prove is that there's no loop besides the $1 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$ one. Otherwise the series gets stuck in another loop, whether it decreases or increases doesn't matter anymore. This series cannot fall in loop after a succession of either of the operations alone. As already said, we need a combination of both to increase and decrease from a certain number to get back to it. That means we have in our possible loops at least one odd and one even number. We can start our demonstration from either one.

If we have to schematize mathematically these two conditions, we have to prove that:

$P_o \ll P_E$	<p>P_o is the probability of having to do the $O(u_k) = 3 \times u_k + 1$ operation which is literally the probability of u_k being odd.</p> <p>P_E is the probability of having to do the $E(u_k) = \frac{u_k}{2}$ operation which comes back to finding the probability of u_k being even.</p>
<p>$E^m(O(E^n(O(u_k))))$ is not a possible series of operations in a loop iteration.</p>	<p>Prove that in a loop we can only have one odd operation for it to be a loop. If even two odd operations cannot appear in a loop iteration, more cannot appear either.</p>
<p>$u_{k+1} = 3 \times u_k + 1 = 2^n \times u_k$ means that $u_k = 1$</p>	<p>This series can fall in a loop only if the odd operation on u_n you get a number that is a power of 2 times u_k so that after applying a certain number of the even operation we fall back to u_k.</p>

Proof that the series cannot go up to infinity

If u_0 is even, a list of even operations will be applied on it till it becomes its biggest odd factor. So, we can just assume that u_0 is odd for the rest of our proof.

u_0 being odd, we have to apply the odd operation to it and u_1 becomes even. So, for each iteration of the odd operation $O(u_k)$ there's at least one $E(u_{k+1})$ that reduces the result. But alone $O(u_k)$ provides a greater increase than the decrease forced by $E(u_{k+1})$. So just based on that observation, we could be tempted to say that the series will ultimately go up to infinity but from the few test cases we have we know that is not true.

What's the trick?

We have already shown that if u_k is odd, u_{k+1} is even. That means there cannot be two consecutives odd operations. While we have an infinite number of both even and odd numbers in mathematics, there's a greater quantity of even numbers than odd numbers in any one series following the rules of Collatz conjecture. Note that if there's twice the quantity of even operation $E(u_k)$ compared to the quantity of odd operation $O(u_k)$, the series will inevitably fall towards its minimum value because for each increase of 3 times plus 1, there's two decreases for a total of a division by 4.

If we manage to prove that the frequency of $E(u_k)$ is at least 2 times greater than the frequency of $O(u_k)$, we will be done.

We have to consider here the even numbers or rather the chance of getting an odd number after i iterations of the even operations. Finding i is the problem as i has to be greater than 2 to justify our hypothesis.

Applying the odd operation on an odd number guarantee an even number:

$$P_{i(o_u)=1} = 100\%$$

After one iteration of the odd operation we get an even number we can write like this: $u_k = 2^p \times o$ where o is an odd number and p is a positive integer greater or equal to 1.

Counting the number of iterations of the even operations before encountering an odd number in that case means finding the value of p .

We know $p \geq 1$ and is random. p could be any other number than 1 like 2; 3; 4; 5; ...; ∞ . That means that the probability of p being 1 is close to zero.

$$P_{i(E_u) \geq 2} = P_{p \neq 1} \approx 1$$

$$P_{i(E_u)=1} = P_{p=1} = 1 - P_{p \neq 1} \approx 0$$

Conclusion

With a great number of iterations, the quantity of even numbers will greatly exceed the quantity of odd numbers meaning the series will ultimately decrease no matter its initial value.

Determining the loop

$$\Rightarrow u_{k+1} = 3 \times u_k + 1 = 2^n \times u_k \text{ with } n \text{ a positive integer}$$

$$\Rightarrow u_k \times (2^n - 3) = 1$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{u_k} = 2^n - 3$$

$$\Rightarrow u_k = 1 \text{ and } n = 2$$

Conclusion

The only possible loop following this format is $1 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$ with two even operations and one odd operation.

Only one odd operation in a loop

$E^m(O(E^n(O(u_k)))) = u_k$ with n and m positive integers and u_k is an odd positive number

$$\Rightarrow \frac{3 \times \left(\frac{3 \times u_k + 1}{2^n} \right) + 1}{2^m} = u_k$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{9 \times u_k + 3 + 2^n}{2^{n+m}} = u_k$$

$$\Rightarrow 9 \times u_k + 3 + 2^n = 2^{n+m} \times u_k$$

$$\Rightarrow 9 \times u_k + 3 = 2^{n+m} \times u_k - 2^n$$

$$\Rightarrow 3 \times (u_k + 1) = 2^n \times (2^m \times u_k - 1)$$

2^n is even and $2^m \times u_k - 1$ is odd

By substitution:

- $2^n = u_k + 1$
- $2^m \times u_k - 1 = 3$

By resolving this system, we get $u_k = 1$; $m = n = 2$.

That proves that $E^n(O(u_k))$ was the loop and all we did was one additional iteration of it.